

RE-DWELL Summer School 1 (Nicosia)

Deliverable 3.4

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 3.4 RE-DWELL Summer School 1 (Nicosia)

Version 1

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Executive summary

Three, five-day international summer schools have been planned to take place in Nicosia (m12), Valencia (m24) and Reading (m36) as part of the RE-DWELL project. The first of these summer schools, organized by the University of Cyprus (UCY), has been carried out during the second year of the project activities in Nicosia, from November 15 to 20, 2021. This report focuses on the results of this summer school.

The programme of activities of the Nicosia summer school aimed at fostering the exchange of knowledge across early-stage researchers (ESRs), supervisors and non-academic organisations, on the challenges and opportunities of the design process in realizing needs for affordable and sustainable housing. The theme of the summer school, “Planning, Design and Retrofitting of Affordable and Sustainable Housing”, was thus addressed from multiple perspectives through presentations from invited speakers from professional practice, academia, the local partner organisation and the local municipalities. The presentations were followed by insightful group discussions and were complemented by site visits to the Nicosia Master Plan’s regeneration projects (north and south Nicosia) and the local partner organisation’s (CLDC, Cyprus Land Development Corporation) housing projects in the city of Limassol. A roundtable to discuss “The design of affordable and sustainable housing: challenges and opportunities” was open to the public via an online session.

The programme of activities also enabled a follow-up on the development of ESR’s research through training activities related to the ongoing structured courses (two sessions on “Research, Methods and Tools 1” and “Transferrable Skills 1”).

15 ESRs (in-person), 14 supervisors/co-supervisors (5 in-person, 9 online), 5 partner organisations (online) and one local partner organisation (in-person) participated in the summer school. Some preparatory work was carried out by the ESRs to enable them to reflect on the potential role of the secondments in their individual research thesis, on the work of their peers and on examples of good practices in the field of affordable and sustainable housing.

Participants evaluated the course through an online survey (Annex 1), the results of which are presented in Section 2.2. The overall organisation of the summer school scored high (4.67 out of 5 points). The written feedback highlights that the summer school succeeded in addressing the theme from multiple perspectives and activities (diversity of presenters’ backgrounds, guided site visits, debates/roundtables, documentary).

Important takeaways for the design of future summer schools/workshops include an early introduction to the local context, involvement and suggestions of ESRs as regards the planned activities, broader representation of the different disciplines involved in housing studies (social, economic, architectural) through the lectures/roundtables. Also, ESRs expressed a preference for more interactive sessions and discussion time and shorter lectures, as well as more guidance on tasks that they have to prepare in advance.

The work carried out in the Nicosia summer school fostered an understanding of the significance and impact of the planning and design process when dealing with affordable and sustainable housing in Europe. The multiplicity of factors involved in a research approach engaging diverse stakeholders (non-academics, local municipalities, civic society) were addressed through the summer school’s activities and can inform forthcoming RE-DWELL activities.

1. Introduction

This report summarizes the work done during the first RE-DWELL summer school held in Nicosia, from November 15 to 20, 2021, organized by the University of Cyprus (UCY). It encompasses the activities done by early-stage researchers (ESRs) prior to the workshop, the sessions facilitated by the tutors of RTM1 and TS1 courses, the programme of activities (ESRs research project presentations, onsite and online lectures and site visits), the outputs of the workshop, and the evaluation of the programme by ESRs and supervisors/co-supervisors.

The programme of the Nicosia summer school aimed at fostering the exchange of knowledge across ESRs, supervisors and non-academic organisations, on the challenges and opportunities of the design process in realizing needs for affordable and sustainable housing. The programme of activities was thus designed to enable a follow-up on the development of ESR's research through training activities related to the ongoing structured courses (two sessions on "Research, Methods and Tools 1-RMT1" and "Transferrable Skills 1-TS1") and through networking activities between the individual projects, supervisors/co-supervisors and partner organisations.

The summer school addressed the theme of "Planning, Design and Retrofitting of Affordable and Sustainable Housing" and the programme encompassed five sub-themes which are part of the RE-DWELL training structure:

- **The design of affordable and sustainable housing** – challenges and opportunities that affordable and sustainable housing planning and design poses for architects and planners, developers and inhabitants; collaborative housing, co-production, social innovation, and social experimentation in housing and neighbourhoods; understanding the building/community relationships and opportunities.
- **Transdisciplinarity research for affordable and sustainable housing** – appropriate theoretical grounding of the ESRs' research projects in a transdisciplinary manner; analysis and position of own research and that of another ESR within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines; analysis of different research approaches to housing in terms of research aims, theoretical backgrounds and methods (interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity, etc.)
- **Social housing design** – factors involved in the design of social housing; financial models and incentives; community resilience through community planning for housing development; encouraging participation, enabling cogeneration of housing schemes.
- **Innovative research in sustainability and the importance of ethics in research** – challenges and opportunities of conducting research; ethics, open science and intellectual property rights; ethics, principles and sustainability; ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management.
- **Sustainable planning and design for affordable housing in listed neighbourhoods** – challenges in neighbourhood regeneration projects; retrofitting; adaptively reusing building stock at the scale of the building and the scale of the neighbourhood; environmental and bioclimatic design: Learning from the past, applying to today's challenges; social sustainability in a time of population shifts.

Invited speakers from professional practice, academia, the local partner organisation and the local municipalities addressed topics related to the summer school's theme. The lectures were followed by insightful group discussions and were complemented by site visits to the Nicosia Master Plan's regeneration projects (north and south Nicosia) and to the local partner organisation's (CLDC, Cyprus Land Development Corporation) housing projects in the city of Limassol. A roundtable to discuss "The design of affordable and sustainable housing: challenges and opportunities" was moderated by Leandro Madrazo, La Salle-URL, and was open to the public via an online session.

Some preparatory work was carried out by the ESRs which included: meetings with the supervisors/secondments before the summer school to discuss the potential role of the secondments in their individual research thesis; a peer-review report of the essay submitted by another ESR for the course RMT1; an optional informal presentation of a case study/example of good practice in the field of affordable and sustainable housing; and suggestions on discussion topics of interest for the panel organised by UCY on sustainable planning and design for affordable housing in listed neighbourhoods.

Throughout the different activities of the programme, ESRs had the opportunity to demonstrate their ability to analyse and position their own research and that of another ESRs within the field of housing studies, to reflect on their own research work and on the work of their peers, to present and communicate this reflection to both academics and non-academics, to improve their understanding of transdisciplinary research methodologies in general and in relation to their own projects, to improve their understanding of the challenges and opportunities of conducting research and the ethical considerations involved and to engage with several external Cypriot stakeholders.

The structure and outcome of RE-DWELL's summer schools can provide an insightful resource for academics and researchers within the field of housing studies, fostering an understanding of the compatibility between affordable and sustainable housing across Europe through a holistic and transdisciplinary research and training programme.

1.1. Contribution of local partners

The University of Cyprus (UCY) had the responsibility of organising the summer school. A fruitful collaboration, established with local non-academic organisations, enriched the program of the summer school and strengthened the ties with different and diverse stakeholders involved in the housing sector. The local partner organisation, Cyprus Land Development Corporation (CLDC), the municipalities of Nicosia and Limassol, the Cyprus Energy Agency, the Nicosia Master Plan team and the Nicosia Development Agency, played a key role in accomplishing the learning objectives of the summer school (site visits to the Nicosia Master Plan's regeneration projects (north and south Nicosia) and to the local partner organisation's (CLDC, (Cyprus Land and Development Corporation) housing projects in the city of Limassol). CLDC was in charge of organizing one session of the programme on social housing design, the Nicosia Municipality facilitated the site visit to the Nicosia Master Plan's regeneration projects and the Limassol Municipality kindly provided the facilities for the activities in the city of Limassol.

1.2. Participants

There were 50 participants, including ESRs, supervisors/co-supervisors, guest speakers and partners, who engaged in activities and exchanged knowledge on the challenges and opportunities of the design process in realizing needs for affordable and sustainable housing. From RE-DWELL, 15 ESRs (in-person), 14 supervisors/co-supervisors (5 in-person, 9 online), 5 partner organisations (online) and one local partner organisation (in-person) participated in the summer school (Figure 5):

- B1 FUNITEC (La Salle-URL), Spain, Project Coordinator (in-person)
- B2 University Grenoble Alpes, France (in-person and online)
- B3 University of Sheffield, United Kingdom (online)
- B4 University of Zagreb, Croatia (online)
- B5 Hungarian Academy of Sciences Centre of Excellence, Hungary (online)
- B6 University of Cyprus, Cyprus (in-person)
- B7 Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain (in-person)
- B8 TU Delft, Netherlands (online)
- B9 ISCTE- Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Portugal (online)
- B10 University of Reading, United Kingdom (online)
- PO8 Cyprus Land and Development Corporation (in-person)

Figure 5. Nicosia summer school participants

1.3. RTM and TS training activities

A follow-up on the development of ESR's research was facilitated through training activities related to the ongoing structured courses : "RMT1- Research, Methods and Tools 1" (Figure 1) and "TS1- Transferrable Skills" (Figure 2).

Figure 1. RMT1 course structure as integrated with the network activities.
 From: Adriana Diaconu (UGA), Research Methods and Tools 1 (RMT1)

Figure 2. TS1 course structure as integrated with the network activities.
 From: Karim Hadjri (USFD), Transferable Skills 1 (TS1)

1.4. Dissemination

Dissemination activities, aiming at reaching and positively influencing relevant stakeholders and end users through their direct or indirect engagement with the summer school's activities and outcomes, were performed before, during and after the event. The implemented dissemination activities aimed at informing researchers, local associations, professors, PhD students, policy makers and the general public about the aims, activities and the outcomes of the Nicosia summer school's outcomes.

To this end, the event was disseminated in different media including UCY and RE-DWELL social media channels (Figure 3) before and during the activities (Instagram, Twitter and Facebook).

After the end of the workshop, ESRs published some reflections about their experiences in the [RE-DWELL blog](#). The video of the roundtable is uploaded to the [RE-DWELL YouTube channel](#).

Figure 3. Dissemination in UCY and RE-DWELL Twitter

2. Programme

The summer school was carried out at the Learning Resource Centre UCY Library “Stelios Ioannou”, Nicosia, from November 15 to 20, 2021. It was carried out in person, but was conditioned by the COVID-19 security recommendations in force in Cyprus and Europe at the time. Thus, all the sections were in hybrid mode (in-person and online).

The programme was divided in daily sessions/themes in an attempt to link the training and research activities taking place within RE-DWELL with relevant expertise and activities of external stakeholders from professional practice, academia and local municipalities, and site visits (Table 1).

Table 1. Programme of the summer school

Day	Timetable	Activities
FIRST DAY Tuesday, November 16, 2021	10:00 to 10:30	Welcome
	10:30 to 12:00	ESRs' Research Projects and Secondments
	12:00 to 13:00	Meeting with Partner Organizations
	13:00 to 14:15	Lunch break
	14:15 to 16:00	ESR Review Meeting #1
	14:15 to 16:00	Roundtable
	20:00	Dinner
SECOND DAY Wednesday, November 17, 2021	10:00 to 12:45	RMT1: peer-review presentations
	13:00 to 14:15	Lunch break
	14:15 to 16:30	RMT1: peer-review presentations
	16:30 to 18:15	ESR Review Meeting #2
	20:00	Dinner
THIRD DAY Thursday, November 18, 2021	09:00 to 10:15	CLDC Session
	10:30 to 11:45	Trip to Limassol
	11:45 to 13:15	Guided Tour in Limassol
	13:30 to 15:00	Lunch break
	15:00 to 16:00	Presentation of case studies
	16:00 to 17:30	Case studies: ESRs' presentations
	17:30 to 18:30	Cocktail
FOURTH DAY Friday, November 19, 2021	10:00 to 13:00	TS1: Open discussion
	13:00 to 14:15	Lunch break
	14:30 to 16:15	ESR Review Meeting #3
FIFTH DAY Saturday, November 20, 2021	09:00 to 10:00	UCY session
	10:00 to 12:00	Guided "Walkshop"
	12:00 to 13:30	Supervisory Board meeting
	13:30 to 14:45	Lunch break
	15:00 to 18:00	Learning from the past
	18:30 to 20:00	Documentary "Anamones"
	20:00	Dinner

The activities carried out on each day of the programme are described in the following section.

2.1. Activities

FIRST DAY

Tuesday, November 16th

Welcome

- Leandro Madrazo, RE-DWELL Project Coordinator
- Prof. Tasos Christofidis, Rector, University of Cyprus
- Charalambos Iacovou, Cyprus Land Development Corporation
- Nadia Charalambous, Department of Architecture, UCY

Individual Research Projects Networking – Reflection on the role of secondments

Based on the outcome of the meetings with the supervisors/secondments before the summer school, ESRs met in this hands-on session with peers in clusters of two, to exchange information about their contacts with partner organisations and to discuss the potential role of the secondments in their individual research thesis (Figure 4).

Figure 4. ESR projects networking session

The outcome of their discussion was posted panels (Figure 5). The thirty-minute activity was followed by a presentation by each group, which received the feedback from the participants (ESRs, supervisors, co-supervisors and secondment representatives) (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Individual Research Projects Networking session – Mapping

Figure 6. Individual Research Projects Networking. Group presentation and discussion with ESRs, supervisors, co-supervisors and secondment representatives

ESR Review Meeting #1

During the first part of the afternoon, group meetings of each ESR with supervisors, co-supervisors and secondment representatives took place.

Roundtable discussion: “The Design of Affordable and Sustainable Housing: Challenges and Opportunities”

An open discussion on the design of affordable and sustainable housing focusing on the challenges and opportunities during the design process, was moderated in the afternoon session by Leandro Madrazo, La Salle-URL, Project Coordinator.

The sub-theme that guided the structure of the session was the challenges and opportunities during the design of affordable and sustainable housing. Guest speakers were:

- Assoc. Prof. Darinka Czischke, TU Delft
- Assoc. Prof. Lisa D. Iulo, Director of the Hamer Center for Community Design, Pennsylvania State University
- Assoc. Prof. Montserrat Pareja Eastaway, University of Barcelona

The speakers discussed the challenges and opportunities that affordable and sustainable housing planning and design poses for architects and planners, developers and inhabitants, forms of collaborative housing, co-production, social innovation, and social experimentation in housing and neighbourhoods and the building/community relationships and opportunities.

The presentations were followed by a fruitful Q&A session and a discussion session with the ESRs (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Round Table open online discussion

[The video of the roundtable](#) is available in the RE-DWELL website.

SECOND DAY

Wednesday, November 17th

RMT1 Research Methodologies and Tools: peer-review presentations

Facilitator: Adriana Diaconu, University of Grenoble

RTM1 training activities on the sub-theme of “Transdisciplinarity Research for Affordable and Sustainable Housing” were organized in two slots (morning session and afternoon session).

During the morning session, ESRs critically presented the essay written by another peer (Figure 8). The five-minute presentations focused on the integration of the topics of RMT1 (“transdisciplinarity”, “affordability”, “sustainability”) in the research projects. Each presentation was followed by a discussion led by a staff member from the RE-DWELL network.

Figure 8. ESRs presentations of the essay written by another peer

Based on these presentations, a collective mapping of the disciplinary approaches put forward by the different research projects was elaborated through the Miro platform (Figure 9). This second map reflected the structure acquired by the network, first five months after the initial mapping exercise realized during the Introductory days.

Figure 9. Collective map of the ESRs' research. Source: Adriana Diaconu, UGA

ESR Review Meeting #2

During the rest of the afternoon, group meetings of each ESR with supervisors, co-supervisors and secondment representatives took place.

THIRD DAY

Thursday, November 18th

Cyprus Land Development Corporation (CLDC) Session: “The Design of Sustainable and Affordable Housing”, Facilitator: Charalambous Iacovou, CLDC.

The session included three presentations from invited speakers from professional practice, and members of the local partner organization during the morning and a site visit in the municipality of Limassol where a number of affordable housing projects provided by CLDC are located, in the afternoon.

– CLDC, Nicosia

Charalambos Iacovou and Kiki Papasozomenou presented the aims, activities and projects of the Cyprus Land Development Corporation. This was followed by two twenty-minute presentations of the awarded design proposals of relevant architectural competitions initiated by CLDC (Figure 10).

*Figure 10. Charalambos Iacovou, Kiki Papasozomenou.
Cyprus Land Development Corporation: Aims and Projects*

– Elina Pattichi, EP Architects

Presentation of the Winning Design Proposal for Social Housing in Pano Polemidia in Limassol, Cyprus Land Development Corporation (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Presentation by Elina Pattichi

– **Spyros Spyrou, NOA**

Presentation of Firm's Design Proposal for Social Housing in Pano Polemidia in Limassol of Cyprus Land Development Corporation (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Presentation by Spyros Spyrou

The presentations were followed by questions and answers and a fruitful discussion with the ESRs (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Questions and answers with presenters

Guided Tour - CLDC Housing Projects in the city of Limassol

The case studies presentations during the morning session were complemented by the site visit in the city of Limassol which aimed at introducing the summer school participants to local case studies of affordable housing projects provided by CLDC, their design, their context as well as the profile of their residents (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Housing Projects by CLDC

Presentation of case studies of sustainable housing: Eco-neighbourhoods case study, Larnaca Municipality

Facilitator: Iraklis Achnotis, District Officer, Town Planning Department, Limassol

Municipal Cultural Centre Panos Solomonidis

The session continued with a presentation of a case study on eco-neighbourhoods facilitated by the District Officer of the Town Planning Department (Figure 15). The design approach, construction methods, materials, and environmental concerns were discussed with the ESRs.

Figure 15. Eco-neighbourhoods case study presentation

Case studies: ESRs' presentations

The day was concluded with an informal session dedicated to share with peers and supervisors, examples of good practices/case studies in the field of affordable and sustainable housing. The concept of a “case-study” in relation with individual research was discussed and facilitated by the ESRs (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Informal session on examples of good practices

FOURTH DAY

Friday, November 19th

Transferable Skills (TS1) open discussion: “Innovative research in sustainability and the importance of ethics in research”

TS1 activities included a debate on “Innovative research in sustainability and the importance of ethics in research”, moderated by Karim Hadjri, University of Sheffield.

Three guest researchers discussed, through their research work and experience, innovative research approaches addressing ethical considerations and the challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management:

- Prof. Renata Tyszczyk, Chair in Architectural Humanities, School of Architecture, University of Sheffield, UK
- Assoc. Prof. Agata Justyna Twardoch, The Silesian University of Technology, Faculty of Architecture, Department of Urban and Country Planning, Gliwice, Poland
- Dr. Una Lynch, Director of Sonrisa Solutions Limited, Banbridge, Northern Ireland

The discussion focused on innovative research approaches addressing ethical considerations and the challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management. The presentations were followed by a thirty-minute Q&A discussion at the end, moderated by ESRs (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Transferable Skills session

ESR Review Meeting #3

During the afternoon, group meetings of each ESR with supervisors, co-supervisors and secondment representatives took place.

FIFTH DAY

Saturday, November 20th

University of Cyprus (UCY) session: Sustainable and affordable housing in historic city centres.

Facilitators: Dr. Nadia Charalambous, Dr. Andreas Savvides, Department of Architecture, University of Cyprus

This session was dedicated to sustainable planning and design for affordable housing in listed neighbourhoods.

– Nicosia Master Plan and site visit in regeneration projects initiated by the municipality of Nicosia

Facilitator: Athina Papadopoulou, Nicosia Master Plan Office, Head at Nicosia Municipality

During the morning session, the bicommunal Nicosia Master Plan was presented by the Head of the Nicosia Master Plan Office (Figure 18). Participants were informed about the aims, activities, projects and strategies of the Plan which aimed at dealing with the planning challenges posed by the divided city of Nicosia through the collaboration of the city's two communities and under the auspices and the financial backing of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The activities of the team aim at improving the living conditions of the residents of the historic centre through the regeneration of “twin” neighbourhoods, in the north and south parts of the city respectively.

Figure 18. Nicosia Master Plan presentation

The thirty-minute presentation of the bicommunal Nicosia Master Plan, was followed by a thirty-minute Q&A discussion at the end, facilitated by the ESRs.

Guided workshop in north & south Nicosia – Visit two housing regeneration projects in Chrysaliniotissa and Arabahmet neighbourhoods.

The presentation was complemented by a site visit in order to see in practice the activities and projects of the Nicosia Master Plan team. Two neighbourhoods which were regenerated in parallel in the south and the north were visited and the challenges faced were discussed (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Chrysaliniotissa and Arabahmet neighbourhoods' projects

Supervisory Board meeting

During the day, a reflection meeting with supervisors, co-supervisors, partner organisations and ESRs took place after the guided tour.

Learning from the past

Facilitators: Effrosyni Roussou and Andreas Panagidis

There were two ten-minute presentations, followed by a thirty-minute Q&A discussion at the end, moderated by the ESRs

– UCY Academics presentations: Sustainable Planning and design for affordable housing in listed neighbourhoods

The presentations addressed the following issues:

- Making decisions / choices on materials and methods of construction in new-built or renovated cases.
- Environmental and bioclimatic design: Learning from the past, applying to the contemporary.

- Adaptively reusing building stock: the scale of the building and the scale of the neighbourhood
- Rehabilitation and Reprogramming at the scale of the unit and the scale of the building block or neighbourhood

The presenters were:

- Maria Philokyprou, Associate Professor, Department of Architecture, UCY

Rehabilitation of Traditional Dwellings

- Aimilios Michael, Assistant Professor, Department of Architecture, UCY, Sustainability and Conservation of Modern Architecture: The Alexander Demetriou Building, Nicosia, Cyprus (Figure 20)
- Andreas Savvides, Associate Professor, Department of Architecture, UCY, Revitalizing Social Housing (Figure 21)

Figure 20. Presentation by Aimilios Michael

Figure 21. Presentation by Andreas Savvides

– External UCY collaborators presentations: Sustainability in a time of population shifts.

The presentations addressed the following issues:

- Community resilience through community planning for housing development
- Population integration: the locals and the newcomers
- Empowering immigrants: finding their voice, claiming their future
- Encouraging participation, enabling cogeneration of housing schemes

The presenters were:

- Marina Kyriakou, Cyprus Energy Agency: sustainability projects (Figure 22)
- Yeitonia +: participatory re-design of residential streets
- Eleftherios Loizou, Managing Director, Nicosia Development Agency: engaging the stakeholders: the Connecting Nature Project (Figure 23)

Figure 22. Presentation by Marina Kyriakou

Figure 23. Presentation by Eleftherios Loizou

Documentary screening “Anamones”

The day concluded with the screening of the documentary “Anamones”, which examines the sociological aspect of the rusty starter bars sticking out of the rooftops for “future use” (Figure 24). The screening was followed by a discussion with representatives of Stephanos Papadas (audiovisual artist), Andri Tsiouti (architect), Michalis Charalambous (visual artist) and Gorges Stylianou (audiovisual artist) who collaborated on the production of the documentary.

Figure 24. Documentary screening and discussion

2.2. Evaluation

The workshop was evaluated by all the participants (in-person and online), through an anonymous online questionnaire (see Annex 1). The main goal of the questionnaire was to evaluate their experience and to detect any elements that could be improved in future workshops and summer schools.

The online questionnaire was answered by 12 ESRs, 3 supervisors/co-supervisors and 1 partner organization.

In the first part of the survey participants were asked to assign a rating a general view. In the second part, they had to identify what they particularly liked and what could have been done better. At the end of the survey, they could add comments and recommendations for upcoming network activities (see Annex 1 - Event evaluation form) .

All the sessions were generally well appreciated (Table 2). The majority of the participants evaluated positively the overall organization of the summer school (average 4.46).

Table 2. Nicosia Workshop: online evaluation

Questions	Answers	Supervisors / Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
How would you rate the organization of the workshop? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	16	4.5	4.25	4.4
Please evaluate ESRs Research Projects and Secondments session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	15	4	3.92	3.96
Please evaluate Meeting with Partner Organisations session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	3.5	3	3.25
Please evaluate CLDC session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4.5	3.67	4.1
Please evaluate Roundtable session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4.5	4.6	4.55
Please evaluate UCY and Nicosia Municipality sessions (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	16	5	3.76	4.4
Please evaluate Transferrable Skills session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	4	3.75	3.9
Please evaluate Research Methodologies and Tools session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	15	4.66	4.5	4.58

The majority of the ESRs answered positively to the “Research Projects and secondments” session:

“It was good practice to explain our projects to each other and find the similarities that we could help each other with, in the future. We also exchanged ideas about what we can do in the secondments. In addition, we discussed about what are our main concerns, potential challenges and what information we need to ask the secondments about”.

“It was very useful to discuss with another ESR about our common secondment. We went through the secondment’s publications and areas of interest and we exchanged opinions about how that could fit in the research”.

“Great interactive way to share secondment insights with fellow ESRs”.

“It was a very good opportunity to discover new connections between what seemed as not so related projects and a great way to brainstorm on what the role of secondments could be, before the individual meetings with the secondment partners”.

“Very interesting hands on workshop (poster session) in the first part and well paired ESRs to understand possible collaboration and specific interests”.

However, some ESR mentioned that:

“The feed-back they have received was not sufficient for most of them to overcome difficulties and move forward”

“ It would be great to have some feedback and discussion with the rest of the group on our presentations”.

Regarding the “Meeting with Partner Organizations” session, the rating varied between the ESRs since in some cases representatives of the partner organisations did not attend the meetings. Relevant comments:

“From my point of view the meeting with the partners wasn’t so useful because they could have particular session in the evening and this could be useful in order to review all the proposals and summarize them”.

“It was not very effective for me as my secondment representatives were not there. But I got some ideas from the whole discussion to understand what others are doing”.

Regarding the “ESR Review Meetings” sessions, the rating was mostly positive but it did again vary between the ESRs since in some cases representatives of the partner organisations did not attend the meetings. Relevant comments:

“Slightly forced, and not particularly relevant as all ESRs had conversations with their supervisors prior to the Nicosia summer school. Also, this idea should have been communicated to ESRs a lot earlier”.

“My own meeting went very smoothly, all the parties involved were present. However, it was quite evident that a lot of my colleagues were unsure on whether it was us that should be informing our partners to join the meeting or if they would have been centrally informed through the programme itself”.

Regarding the “Roundtable” session, it was positively rated by all ESRs. These comments exemplify the general view:

“Great speakers, particularly Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway and Darinka Czischke, and great amount of female representation compared to Lisbon”.

“It was great to have such a diverse panel. It was much appreciated that non-architects were invited to share their insights”.

“Very good speakers and relevant for my topic. Great gender consideration. I learned about new interesting angles on how to expand my research”.

“It was a very interesting session, rich in content and perspectives about the role of architects in the creation of affordability and sustainability in housing. It was great to see three experts from different countries and contexts analysing the key aspects that can enable a paradigm shift in housing practices in Europe and the US”.

“High level presentations and discussion and very engaging for all ESRs to participate”.

“Excellent initiative. The roundtable is a great way to listen to people who are at the forefront and experts on their fields and also to open discussions with great value for our topics. It was informative, but also insightful as we were also hearing their opinion

and critic on what work/ doesn't work or where is the gap, which is highly useful in order to orient our research”.

Nevertheless, the need for more time to discuss with the guests was mentioned.

“Interesting but I wish ESR had more time to ask more questions. Moreover, it would be good to let the guests make very simple presentation so we can relate”.

All ESRs answered positively to the “Research Methodologies and Tools” session. These comments exemplify the general view:

“It was mainly a peer review of RMT1 essays and not focussing on Research Methodologies and Tools. Our essays were focussing more on the transdisciplinary. For the peer review, It was very useful for me to get an idea of what am I missing and what do I need to further define. The comments of the reviewer (Professor) for me were very valuable”.

“This was wonderful. One cannot underestimate the value of a peer review, and I particularly liked that we had the time for in-depth feedback. It also helped to better understand the projects of the fellow ESRs”.

“It was a fantastic opportunity to hear how my peers think and how they explain academic concepts”.

“Great experience to be able to attempt to give feedback and learn what the other ESR and supervisors feedback were. Very useful and relevant to also hear everyone else's peer review. This helped to clarify writing issues that can be improved in my writing going forward”.

Some ESRs mentioned that:

“However, some peer review of other ESRs sounds aggressive and I did not like that. I wish next time to have a guideline about how to do a peer review properly”.

“It was interesting to go through this, although I truly wish we had some more time to prepare, for me it was quite stressful. Also, there weren't any real guidelines for this, so everyone interpreted in a different way...”

As regards the session facilitated by the Cyprus Land Development Corporation (CLDC), there was overall positive feedback,

“It was a necessary session to get some in-depth context and insights about the housing issues in Cyprus. The presentations were interesting, especially the ones from the invited architects”

“Very interesting to see a perspective by a Land Development Corporation. Especially for people working on participatory processes, the discussion with stakeholders with whom we don't necessarily share the same values/opinions can be a very didactic experience and offer a drop of reality. It is within these conflicting perspectives that we

can develop a common ground and boost our research. Please give us more like this sessions in the future”.

“Great discussion had by all on site where everyone was able to jump in and give opinions and share insights”.

“It was very interesting discussion from a real practice and market point of view. It revealed the real problems the housing associations face to turn an affordable housing project into a reality and what lessons did they learned from previous experiences. One of the main lessons was the need for maintenance to be controlled by the housing association and not the residents to guarantee a certain quality of the common spaces. Discussions about how the housing construction costs influence the realization of these projects, were very useful”.

ESRs noted the following:

“Perhaps we could ask the CLDC representatives for shorter presentations (or two rather than four), as the debate afterwards was more interesting than the PowerPoint slides”.

“Informative presentations. Different perspectives to the housing projects (urban, economical, historical, etc.), in addition to the architectural approach would have been appreciated”.

The “Guided Tour in Limassol” session was less favourably evaluated; comments included:

“ It would be better to have a contextual overview of the area before going in order to understand better the place”.

“It was nice and well-organised, although I always have this feeling that we see these projects almost as if they’re in a vacuum. We get no particular feel of the context they have bloomed in which subsequently leads to a quite narrow perspective and opinion, heavily based on taking for granted what we hear from those presenting/guiding. I am aware that time limitations would not allow for a bigger introduction to the city, how it developed, factors that enabled or hindered it, and how such projects as the ones we saw fell into place, what their implications were etc. But maybe we can find a middle solution in the future”.

The “Presentation of case studies of sustainable housing” session was positively received by most ESRs:

“Very interesting to hear their plans, which seemed quite controversial. A good insight into the reality of how planning works in Cyprus”.

“Great first effort to work on case studies”.

“Very good and informative session, good work done by the colleagues. Interesting speaker in the session on Limassol”.

“Good presentations and it was an opportunity to see other factors that are used for case study analysis”.

Yet, ESRs noted the following:

“Pretty interesting, although the size of the room made it difficult for it to become an interactive session”.

The “Case studies: ESRs’ presentations” session received mostly positive feedback:

“I think this was a very good start to our discussion around case studies. It is always nice to feel that it is a collaborative work”.

“It was a notable initiative from my colleagues to start reflecting on the rules and procedures that we all must follow to enrich the RE-DWELL library of case studies. A necessary and relevant first step”.

“Good opportunity to share experiences and views about secondments, fieldwork and the implication of ESRs in the preparation of RE-DWELL's deliverables. The discussion needs to be continued”.

“It was a good opportunity to discuss on what a case study is and how it can be communicated to the others, and also to contemplate on who those “others can be, apart from the re-dwell network. I feel we all have a very different understanding of what a case study is and how it can function within the methodology, so maybe we should be having more sessions on this”.

The “Transferrable Skills” session received mostly positive feedback.

“Very nice presentations and great that we had the time to discuss and raise questions. An interesting debate has risen among us on the role of narratives in research”.

“It was a great idea to have guest speakers as in the roundtable, they offered complementary approaches to the topics treated throughout the seminar. For me, it was particularly interesting the presentation about abandoned housing stock assessment in Poland, and the approach used that mixed quantitative and qualitative methods”.

“It was a very interesting session, and I especially appreciated Una Lynch's presentation, even though i was heavily tearing up. I think branching out into seemingly not so related topics is a breath of fresh air and it helps in gaining different perspectives, rather than strictly sticking to our own mantras”.

ESR mentioned:

“Great speakers, not so much on ethics, but still interesting and relevant topics”.

The “Nicosia Master Plan Presentations” session only received positive feedback:

“I was amazed and inspired by how persistent they were insisting on working towards preserving and improving their city and the historic centre during such an extremely complicated and stressful political situation. It was a completely different experience to learn from”.

“First-hand knowledge, open to questions great expertise”.

“Very comprehensive presentation which provided a good understanding of the divided city and what it means for inhabitants, and the implications of political relationships and EU funding”.

“Very good speaker, interesting session on both sides of Nicosia and what efforts and project had been done in the past to understand the local context”.

“Very informative and useful to understand the Cypriot context. It would have been even greater if this was in the first day of our Summer School and also if the presentation was co-presented by a Turk-Cypriot partner”.

Likewise, the “Guided Walkshop” session received very positive feedback:

“These visits are essential given the type of project we are working on. They allow us to get to know the city a little and to have more information about the houses and the urban structure, and to intuit the economic level of the people who live there”.

“Amazing! and it was very useful to see the different common public spaces and how it differs in terms of maintenance and how much the main entrance of the house impact that! if there is no main entrance opening to that public space, no one take care for it”.

“It was great, I would be happy if we had more of these in the future and not just specific building visits”.

“One of the most significant moments of the summer school. It was very useful to see in real life what was explained in the Master plan presentation. A great mechanism to compare both sides and realize the evident challenges of each. The insights and explanations provided by the guides during the walkshop were rich and complementary to the guided visit”.

Session 1 on “Sustainable Planning and design for affordable housing in listed neighbourhoods”, overall received average feedback:

“Perhaps interesting to understand the wider picture such as mobility issues etc, not necessarily on sustainable and affordable housing provisions”.

“The presentations were insightful, addressing different topics that are relevant for several ESRs”.

“The presentations were nice, but some of them were quite technical which was slightly challenging since everyone was a bit tired at that moment after such a rich schedule”.

ESRs pointed out the following:

“With the end of day tiredness, the presentations were not the most stimulating and sometimes lead onto very specialized topics that may not be relevant to a lot of ESRs”.

“Very technical and very architectural, even for an architect. Far from transdisciplinary”.

Session 2 on “Processes for social sustainability in a time of population shifts”, received mostly positive feedback:

“I enjoyed the two presentations and learning more about the concept of nature-based development and the real example of community participation. The example of community participation proved that stakeholders might think they are proposing the right thing for the neighbourhood residents, which might not be the case in reality”.

“Really great presentation from Marina Kyriakou that enabled me to think more about framing projects with a social agenda and getting insight into the processes and reaction of residents”.

“This on the contrary was super interesting, fresh and action-based participatory processes in contemporary Nicosia”.

“The presentations were insightful, addressing different topics that are relevant for several ESRs”.

“Nice presentations. It was very engaging that all of us sat around for a discussion at the end”.

Yet, it was also mentioned that

“With the end of day tiredness, the presentations were not the most stimulating and sometimes lead onto very specialized topics that may not be relevant to a lot of ESRs”.

Finally, the “Documentary session” received highly positive feedback:

“A really good documentary, perfect to stimulate reflections and discussions: probably what came closest to transdisciplinarity that I have seen yet in the RE-DWELL programme”.

“The documentary itself was a very poetic and amazing closure to our 6-day trip. I personally found it very emotional within its controversies too. Such a clever way to describe and discuss on a social context”.

“It was a great addition to the dynamic. It is something that could be maintained for future events of the network”.

“Perfect documentary to show Cypriot life and the dynamics of family and how this has affected the aesthetics and form of housing here. Appreciated the humour of the film which was a good way to end the week”.

“Great to end with an aesthetic note, really enjoyed it, lively debate afterwards. It'd be great to make room for an artistic moment in future events. A 30 min documentary visit an exhibition, a museum something a bit more light is always nice”.

Regarding other comments or suggestions for upcoming onsite RE-DWELL network activities, some ESRs suggested the following:

“... having any related city tour at the beginning of the workshop or school This would allow us to further explore and understand the context of the city and relate what we saw and our first impression to the local professional presentations”.

“...that the ESRs can be involved even before the activities by suggesting topics, workshops, experts to be invited, or any other idea that they consider linked to their projects and productive for the group”.

“... Research-oriented experts can provide a broader picture even if they are coming from different disciplines, which can be easier connected with one's research topic”.

“regarding roundtables: invite more social scientists and researchers that conduct truly interdisciplinary analyses, perhaps ask ESRs for suggestions ...regarding interactive sessions (such as the peer review), it would be lovely to have more of these”.

“The summer school was very well organized and included many interesting activities. For future network activities, a more balanced involvement of different disciplines and perspectives on housing would be appreciated”.

3. Conclusions

The work carried out in the Nicosia summer school fostered an understanding of the significance and impact of the planning and design process when dealing with affordable and sustainable housing in Europe. The multiplicity of factors involved in a research approach engaging diverse stakeholders (non-academics, local municipalities, civic society) were addressed through the summer school's activities and can inform forthcoming RE-DWELL activities.

Annex 1 – Event evaluation form

RE-DWELL Nicosia Summer School – Quality assessment

16-20 November 2021

This evaluation is to be completed by all participants, ESRs as well as supervisors, co-supervisors, secondment representatives.

Your answers will help to improve the next network activities. Thanks for your cooperation!

* Required

1. Please select your profile *

- a) ESR
- b) Supervisor
- c) Co-supervisor
- d) Secondment

2. How did you attend? *

- a) Online
- b) Onsite
- c) Both

3. How would you rate the organization of the summer school? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

4. Day 1 - Tuesday 16. Please evaluate ESRs' Research Projects and Secondments session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

5. Day 1 - Tuesday 16. Briefly explain the reasons of ESRs' Research Projects and Secondments session evaluation

Open answer

6. Day 1 - Tuesday 16. Please evaluate Meeting with Partner Organizations session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

Open answer

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

7. Day 1 - Tuesday 16. Briefly explain the reasons of Meeting with Partner Organizations session evaluation

Open answer

8. Day 1 - Tuesday 16. Please evaluate ESR Review Meetings session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

9. Day 1 - Tuesday 16. Briefly explain the reasons of ESR Review Meetings session evaluation

Open answer

10. Day 1 - Tuesday 16. Please evaluate Roundtable session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

11. Day 1 - Tuesday 16. Briefly explain the reasons of Roundtable session evaluation

Open answer

12. Day 2 - Wednesday 17. Please evaluate Research Methodologies and Tools session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

13. Day 2 - Wednesday 17. Briefly explain the reasons of Research Methodologies and Tools session evaluation

Open answer

14. Day 3 - Thursday 18. Please evaluate Cyprus Land Development Corporation (CLDC) session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

15. Day 3 - Thursday 18. Briefly explain the reasons of Cyprus Land Development Corporation (CLDC) session evaluation

Open answer

16. Day 3 - Thursday 18. Please evaluate Guided Tour in Limassol session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

17. Day 3 - Thursday 18. Briefly explain the reasons of Guided Tour in Limassol session evaluation

Open answer

18. Day 3 - Thursday 18. Please evaluate Presentation of case studies of sustainable housing session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

19. Day 3 - Thursday 18. Briefly explain the reasons of Presentation of case studies of sustainable housing session evaluation

Open answer

20. Day 3 - Thursday 18. Please evaluate Case studies: ESRs' presentations session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

21. Day 3 - Thursday 18. Briefly explain the reasons of Case studies: ESRs' presentations session evaluation

Open answer

22. Day 4 - Friday 19. Please evaluate Transferable Skills session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

23. Day 4 - Friday 19. Briefly explain the reasons of Transferable Skills session evaluation

Open answer

24. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Please evaluate Nicosia Master Plan Presentations session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3

- d) 4
- e) 5

25. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Briefly explain the reasons of Nicosia Master Plan Presentations session evaluation

Open answer

26. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Please evaluate Guided Walkshop session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

27. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Briefly explain the reasons of Guided Walkshop session evaluation

Open answer

28. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Please evaluate Supervisory Board meeting session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

29. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Briefly explain the reasons of Supervisory Board meeting session evaluation

Open answer

30. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Please evaluate Session 1: Sustainable Planning and design for affordable housing in listed neighbourhoods (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

31. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Briefly explain the reasons of Session 1: Sustainable Planning and design for affordable housing in listed neighbourhoods' evaluation

Open answer

32. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Please evaluate Session 2: Processes for social sustainability in a time of population shifts (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

33. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Briefly explain the reasons of Session 2: Processes for social sustainability in a time of population shifts evaluation

Open answer

34. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Please evaluate Documentary “Anamones” session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

35. Day 5 - Saturday 20. Briefly explain the reasons of Documentary “Anamones” session evaluation

Open answer

36. Any other comments or suggestions for upcoming network activities (workshops, summer schools)

Open answer